

TEXTBOOK EVALUATION "GUESS WHAT"

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Abstract: The textbook *Guess What!* is for young learners in which provides with visual aids, real-world content, and interactive tasks to promote English language learning. The textbook also integrates songs, dialogues, and role-plays that help students develop their language skills. This article provides brief evaluation of the textbook *Guess What!* based on my teaching experiences.

Key words: textbook, content, young learners, learning English, students' need, materials, lesson.

Аннотация: Учебник *Guess What!* предназначен для юных учащихся и содержит наглядные пособия, реальный контент и интерактивные задания для содействия изучению английского языка. В учебник также включены песни, диалоги и ролевые игры, которые помогают учащимся развивать языковые навыки. В данной статье дается краткая оценка учебника *Guess What!* на основе моего педагогического опыта.

Ключевые слова: учебник, содержание, юные ученики, изучение английского языка, потребности учащихся, материалы, урок.

I've selected to evaluate the textbook "Guess What!" series by Susannah Reed (2021) is an engaging course designed for young learners of English. The textbook is known for its rich visual content, incorporating vibrant photography and illustrations to capture children's attention. A key feature is its focus on curiosity-driven learning, where each lesson encourages students to explore real-world topics through fascinating facts and interactive activities. According to Reed and Bentley (2021), the book was carefully chosen and underwent multiple stages of adaptation before reaching your hands to ensure that it could be an enjoyable and fun experience for you. We hope that using this book to learn English will help you reach your future objectives as teachers.

The content of "Guess What" is structured around relatable characters, contextual dialogues, songs, chants, and role-plays. These elements aim to foster both language development and social skills by addressing functional language use and cultural awareness. The course also includes a variety of stories that impart social values, making it suitable for students in primary education.

The textbook is praised for its balanced approach, mixing traditional language exercises with engaging tasks that promote communication and creativity. While it is particularly useful for engaging younger learners, its reliance on visual aids and varied activities helps accommodate different learning styles, making it versatile for diverse classroom settings.

Supplement. In order to meet the needs of each student and provide a detailed explanation of the subject using more real-life examples, I must supply extra materials for this assignment (See exercise No 5. on p. 17)

Justification. Skilled educators are aware of how to meet the needs of their pupils in the classroom by offering extra materials. The majority of textbooks are either inadequate for teaching or practicing the subject matter, or they don't match the ages and language proficiency

of the students. In that situation, teachers ought to give their pupils extra materials to help them reach the objectives.

The process of adding new material to a course-book to make up for gaps in content with the official syllabus, requirements for public exams, or needs of the students is known as supplementation. In order to accommodate the needs of their students and their individual learning styles, teachers frequently offer extra material (McGrath, 2016).

Select. The language proficiency of the students is suitable for this task. As they listen to the audio for this task, students need to select the correct form of each word. It can help pupils become more proficient listeners and comprehenders (See exercise No 6. on p. 17).

Justification. Some texts and activities, according to McGrath (2016), are appropriate for the language proficiency of the pupils and don't need to be modified. It fits with the goals of the lesson.

Replace. This group of students is not suitable for this task. Doing this in the classroom is simple (See exercise No 7. on p. 17).

Justification. I should assign a different task in its place to better meet the needs of my students. There is no excuse for utilizing the original content if it is irrelevant. Unsuitable content, however, may convey crucial learning points because of things like learners' age, interests, cultural background, or past knowledge. Replacing the missing material with more suitable materials is one way to solve the problem partially. McGrath (2016).

Delete. I think it takes too much time to complete this assignment in class, so it should be removed (See exercise No 5. on p. 17).

Justification. We can reject or omit an activity from the textbook if it is time-consuming and irrelevant for the students to complete.

Adapt. All that is needed for this task is reading and listening. This task needs to be modified in order to gain a deeper and better understanding of the passage (See exercise No 17. on p. 21).

Justification. The goals of the lesson are not appropriate for this task. This task has been altered to make it more understandable based on the needs of the students and the lesson objectives. Teaching materials must be tailored to the particular context in order to maximize their appropriateness. Internal features must also be changed to meet the needs of students, teachers, and time constraints. Finally, inherent flaws such as grammatical errors or a lack of variety must be addressed.

References:

1. Reed, S., & Bentley, K. (2015). *Guess What! American English Level 5 Student's Book* (Vol. 5). Cambridge University Press.
2. Reed, S., & Bentley, K. (2015). *Guess What! Level 6 Pupil's Book British English*. Cambridge University Press.